

EDUCATION OF CADETS OF HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN A NATIONAL SPIRIT BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IS A DEMAND OF TODAY

Ismailov Dosbol Tileuberdiyevich,

Head of the General Tactics Cycle - Senior Lecturer, Department of "General Training" of the Southern Operational Command Faculty of the Military Security and Defense University of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Lieutenant Colonel

ANNOTATION

This text covers the modern pedagogical foundations of educating young people in a military-patriotic spirit, the importance of an integrative approach in the process of national education, and the current issues of forming cadets as well-rounded individuals. The theoretical and practical aspects of training competitive military personnel in the context of globalization, increasing their methodological and spiritual potential, and educating in the spirit of loyalty to national values are analyzed. The military-educational reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, conceptual directions aimed at forming patriotic qualities of young people, state policy, and pedagogical mechanisms are also highlighted. Integration in military education, a person-oriented approach, principles of internationalism, and the role of education in the spiritual and moral development of young people are scientifically revealed.

KEYWORDS: patriotism, national education, cadets, integrative approach, military-educational reforms, youth education, national values, personality-oriented education, pedagogical mechanisms, internationalism, military personnel training.

Nowadays, one of the most important issues is the education of young people as a well-rounded person, an advanced person of their Motherland. In the modern dynamic socio-cultural conditions of the world, the need to use human potential as a powerful resource to the maximum is clearly evident. This trend makes the problem of improving the methodology of national education of cadets on the basis of an integrative approach urgent. Because only a well-educated cadet can offer the necessary conditions for achieving a new quality of education and develop scientific activity. In this process, reforms imply the level of improvement of the methodology of national education of cadets on the basis of an integrative approach. Accordingly, in improving the national education of cadets based on an integrative approach, it is important to determine the educational prospects of the future generation and serve the progressive development of society.

In our country, serious attention is paid to the education sector and high demands are being made. Today's globalization and integration process is creating methodological competition. In this regard, there is a need in the labor market for competitive military personnel, a valuable and meaningful attitude to free thinking, and pedagogical personnel with academic knowledge and skills in information and communication and digital technologies and special disciplines. This requires bringing the personal and methodological training of cadets to the level of world standards.

Scientific research is also being conducted to help young people, who are the present and future of the country's peace and development, to have their own personal perspective on the situations taking place in the world, to further develop the spirit of military patriotism in their concern for the

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future of their country, and to improve their skills in making non-standard decisions quickly and independently in any difficult situations.

As in our entire society, major changes are taking place in the activities of our Armed Forces. Our Armed Forces have been rebuilt as one of the guarantors and main symbols of our country's independence. It is difficult to imagine the defense of our state without military personnel with high military-patriotic qualities.

The strength of each country, its place in the world community, and its political and economic development are determined by the potential of its young personnel. In recent years, major reforms have been carried out in the education system in our country, and special attention is paid to the issues of national revival in our state, enriching the minds and worldviews of our youth on the basis of national values, protecting our national army from various foreign ideas, and educating young people to be broad-minded, creative thinkers, high-honored, proud, patriotic, people-oriented, conscientious, enterprising, honest and enthusiastic, and able to make the right decisions in problematic situations. Therefore, it is important to instill in the minds of young people through real examples and effective means that being loyal to the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the military sphere, but also in all aspects of life, being ready to defend them, and being selfless for the country - all these are the demands of today.

The strength of each country, its place in the world community, and its political and economic development are determined by the potential of its young personnel. In recent years, major reforms have been carried out in our country's education system. Today, in a situation where the world is changing rapidly and political, economic, and ideological struggles between regions and countries are becoming increasingly tense, the training of highly patriotic personnel in our republic is one of the most urgent problems today. Therefore, this issue needs to be studied in the practice of all developed foreign countries, and taking into account the results achieved by them in recent years and the emerging military-political situation in the world, it is necessary to consider modern scientific and research work based on an innovative approach in the development of the reserve officer training system as an urgent problem. At the same time, the modern era is characterized by its instability, rapid change, uncertainties, and complexities. In such conditions, systemic changes continue on all fronts.

In recent years, our country has been working to develop military science, adapt it to modern requirements and world standards, train military personnel in military specialties, develop pedagogical mechanisms for educating cadets in the spirit of military patriotism, and improve their military skills.

In-depth study of military conflicts and modern combat operations, as well as the history of national military art, and its improvement in practice have been identified as important priority tasks in the development of military science. This will expand the opportunities for training military personnel with high professional potential in specialized classes in the military-patriotic direction in educational institutions of the Armed Forces system, military education faculties, military academic lyceums of the "Temurbeklar Maktabi" school, general secondary education, and specialized schools.

In our country, educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland, high attention to national and universal values, widely involving the growing younger generation in science, determining measures aimed at uniting them around the idea of "From national revival to national progress!", and uniting them towards a common goal in implementing our state's youth policy also play a special role in the development of young people as patriotic individuals. It should

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also be emphasized that it is a big mistake to allow paperwork, superficiality and inaction in the participation of young people in activities related to military life and physical education. Consequently, the development of new pedagogical technologies for educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism, new innovative methods of patriotic education have become the main goal of current scientific research being conducted today.

In recent years, our republic has been creating a normative basis and material and technical base for educating young people in the spirit of patriotism and increasing the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland. In his address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan on December 20, 2022, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized that “Improving the quality of education is the only way for the development of New Uzbekistan.” This plays a special role in educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism and increasing their inner world and moral commitment.

“A state that relies on new thinking, new ideas, and innovation will win. If we start building our great future today, we must start it on the basis of innovative ideas and an innovative approach,” said the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev. One of the priorities of our state policy is to pay special attention and care to ensure that young people receive a thorough education, master military specialties, and develop in a spirit of respect for our national traditions and values. In this regard, the high work of our teachers, their efforts in educating and imparting knowledge, is highly recognized.

The Concept of “Educating Youth in a Military-Patriotic Spirit”, formulated on the basis of Resolution No. 140 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 23, 2018, emphasizes the need for physically strong and spiritually mature youth in our national army, the understanding that military service is a sacred duty for every citizen of Uzbekistan, as well as theoretical and practical skills in this regard; the formation of skills in young people to approach political and social processes taking place around us and in the world based on our national interests, ideological immunity against various internal and external threats; the need to educate young people who are capable of making quick and independent decisions in any complex situations, and effectively using modern military-technical means.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev has expressed his views with great attention to the education of students and youth in several of his speeches. For example: 1) “The more perfect the education, the happier the people will live... In order for education to be perfect, it is absolutely impossible to allow a gap in this matter.” 2) “Education is our future, a matter of life and death. Therefore, we have no right to postpone reforms in this area.” 3) “No matter how difficult it is, we must find our own unique and effective methods for educating young people, in line with today’s times.” 4) “The problem that troubles me the most is the upbringing of young people. The role of not only parents, but also the neighborhood is incomparable in upbringing.” 5) “The basis and foundation of education and upbringing is the school. The power that makes a school a school is the teachers.” 6) “Our people entrust their greatest wealth – the upbringing of their children – to teachers.” These ideas reflect the urgency of the issue of educating students and youth.

Personalized education means education tailored to the psychological, intellectual, social and spiritual needs of the student. In this approach, the content of education is directly related to the student's life and individual goals. Modern pedagogical science sets the priority task of increasing the effectiveness of education by creating a personalized, customized, competency-based educational process.

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Patriotism is formed in the younger generation through the formation of feelings of joy at the achievements of Uzbekistan in various fields, concern for its prospects, pride in its country, and the preservation of every inch of its land, natural resources, ancient monuments and modern structures, historical values, achievements in science and art, material and spiritual wealth as the apple of their eye.

Today, it is important to form a sense of patriotism in cadets, to educate them in the spirit of love and devotion to the Motherland. For this, they need to form a broad idea of the heritage of our ancestors, the achievements of Uzbekistan, its past and future, its rich culture, spirituality, and scientific potential.

The formation of the state is inextricably linked with the development of a sense of patriotism. A responsible attitude to the state becomes an integral and important part of patriotism in the political environment, thereby acquiring the character of political consciousness.

Patriotism is interconnected with internationalism. Internationalism is the international solidarity of people of different nationalities and races in the world; their mutual understanding and trust, the basis for the interpenetration of cultures, values, knowledge and technologies; the opposite of nationalism. Throughout human history, economic, political, and cultural-spiritual ties have been established and strengthened between different nations and peoples. Without these ties, social progress is impossible.

The Republic of Uzbekistan strives to achieve harmony, cooperation and solidarity with advanced countries in all areas, adhering to the generally recognized rules and principles of international relations. In our country, all citizens, regardless of nationality and race, are working to strengthen mutual trust and solidarity. Representatives of more than 130 nationalities and ethnic groups live in Uzbekistan.

The virtue of internationalism is one of the highest social qualities, a universal spiritual value. In this, young people respect and appreciate the unique spirituality, traditions and culture of other peoples and nationalities. Tolerance is not sufficiently formed in citizens who are indifferent to the spirituality and culture of other nations. Interethnic tolerance, as an important manifestation of internationalism, is of great importance in establishing peace and harmony throughout the world. People with the quality of internationalism prioritize universal human values above all else, regardless of the nationality, religion, and traditions of others. At the current stage of development, internationalism is associated with Uzbekistan's struggle for peace, establishing contacts with scientists, scientists, and artists from different countries in the field of various joint technical, social, and economic projects.

The manifestation of patriotism in a person can be observed in three directions: 1) knowledge - mastering the values inherent in the concept of the Motherland; 2) belief - transforming the acquired knowledge in the field of values into belief; 3) action - demonstrating one's belief through practical activity.

By upbringing, we mean the formation of personal, moral qualities in a person being formed. Upbringing, being closely related to teaching, also has its own laws. Education is a single process. But they are not exactly similar to each other. The unity of education and upbringing lies, first of all, in the commonality of their goals. In a single pedagogical process, education always performs educational tasks, and upbringing performs a responsible task in knowing life, preparing for it. The tasks of upbringing are multifaceted. Upbringing is important in forming the beliefs, moral

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understanding and skills, needs and aspirations of young people who can respond to the laws of our society.

The problem of upbringing and its implementation has been relevant at all times. Because the level of development of a society is measured by the spiritual level of the people living in this society.

Currently, special attention is paid to the problem of integration in the education system. By integration in education, we understand the creative growth of a new active pedagogical team, the skill of using methods that are useful to learners and convenient for their assimilation into their minds. The introduction of integration into the education system can be a key tool in solving educational and upbringing problems that arise between the educational institution and the public. The development of the theory of the use of integration in the teaching process and the development of scientific pedagogical concepts are of fundamental and important importance.

The development of the mechanism of national education of cadets is achieved by forming physically strong and strong individuals who are well-rounded in all respects, strengthening the sense of striving for progress and victory, creating a healthy spirit of competition in military units, having strong ideas and views on the professional specialties of the military service process, military service conditions, getting to know the existing military equipment and weapons, increasing the qualities of courage, bravery, self-sacrifice, heroism, military patriotism, enthusiasm, enthusiasm and honesty, initiative, justice, intelligence, wisdom and happiness, conveying to the youth that the army is a school of true courage, self-sacrifice, true military patriotism, and a reliable source of information for our country's independence, territorial integrity, and the peaceful and prosperous life of our people. We can achieve this goal by forming high aesthetic taste and moral standards, deeply mastering the rich history, culture, traditions and customs of the people of Uzbekistan, increasing love for the Motherland, feelings of pride and honor for the military profession through exhibitions, demonstrations of military equipment, songs and music, and developing admiration and affection for the defender of the Motherland.

The decision to educate cadets of higher military educational institutions in the national spirit based on an integrative approach is characterized by the fact that it is aimed at determining the following aspects: understanding the essence of national education of cadets, their education in the national and combat spirit and military-patriotic; education in the national and combat spirit - the object, subject, types and directions of education in the national and combat spirit in cadets; the place and role of education in the national and combat spirit in the system of professional training of cadets of higher military educational institutions.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that it is the youth who are the future of our state. In this case, the methodology should be based on the general principles of the theory of education, and consist of means, ways and forms of methods for implementing these principles.

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